

Synthesis of Organotin Thiophenols and Evaluation of Their Antifungal and Antibacterial Properties

SURYAMANI BEHERA

Department of Chemistry, S. C. S. College, Puri-752 001 (Orissa)

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Thiophenol and its substituted analogues containing $-CH_3$, $-NH_2$ groups were used for the synthesis of their organotin derivatives through stannation of mercurials using anhydrous stannous chloride in xylene. Their fungicidal and bactericidal properties were studied and found to be quite encouraging.

IN these days of intensive agricultural practices, pesticides are invaluable in the promotion of farm productivity and protection of agricultural products during storage, besides their use in the control of certain vector-borne diseases such as malaria, typhus, yellow fever etc. Among the various synthetic pesticides, mercurated phenols are found to contain bactericidal properties as reported by Guhasircar and Rout^{1,2}.

Similarly Mehrotra and Dey³ have reported pesticides like organotin phenols which are very suitable as the multi-protecting reagents against important fungi and bacteria of cereal crops. Observing the promise of organomercurial and organotin phenols as good pesticides, a few organomercurial and organotin thiophenols have been synthesised and their pesticidal properties (both antifungal and antibacterial) have been evaluated.

Experimental

Thiophenol was mercurated with equimolecular quantities of mercuric acetate in presence of glacial acetic acid and ethyl alcohol⁴. The resultant acetoxymercury thiophenol was converted into its corresponding monochlorotin phenol by refluxing it in dry xylene on an oil bath for 14 hrs with an equimolecular amount of anhydrous stannous

chloride. The tin compound thus formed was then isolated by removing xylene and was then recrystallised in acetone (II, 75%), m.p. 175°. Found: Sn⁴, 45.3%. C₆H₅SnCl requires Sn 45.08%. Their bactericidal behaviours were studied using potato-dextrose agar media. The fungi selected for these studies included *Aspergillus niger* and *Chetomium globossum* and bacteria covering *Staphylococcus aureus* and *Escherichia coli*. The analytical data and the pesticidal properties are given in Table 1.

The structure of the compounds were confirmed on the basis of the position of acetoxymercury group

TABLE 1—NAME OF TIN COMPOUNDS AND THEIR PESTICIDAL PROPERTIES

Sl. No.	Nature of R	m.p.°C	Yield	Colour	Tin Percentage		Pesticidal Properties			
					Found	Calcd	Antifungal		Antibacterial	
							A.N.	C.G.	E.C.	S.A.
1.	H-	175	75%	A	45.3	45.08	+	++	+	++
2.	2-CH ₃	189	60%	Y.W.	43	42.6	+	+	+	+
3.	4-CH ₃	195	40%	Y.W.	42.9	42.6	+	+	+	+
4.	2-NH ₂	210	45%	G.W.	42.7	42.5	++	++	++	++

- Stands negative mortality.
+ Stands mortality upto 50%.
++ Stands mortality more than 50%.
A = Ash.
G = Grey.
Y.W. = Yellowish White.
G.W. = Greyish White.

in the mercurated compounds established earlier by Rohatgi⁵.

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